

Algorithm for adaptive insertion of cohesive elements within computational domain for anticipating crack path

D.Uremović¹ and V.Buljak¹

¹University of Belgrade, Mechanical engineering faculty, Strength of materials department

Abstract:

This paper presents an algorithm for the automatic insertion of cohesive elements within the computational domain. The developed algorithm addresses two key problems relevant to crack simulations: the initiation point of the crack and the direction of its propagation. The results presented here focus on a wedge splitting test, which is commonly used to evaluate fracture properties of quasi-brittle materials. By incorporating cohesive elements, the robustness of the simulations is ensured, as they are straightforward to implement within finite element analysis. Additionally, the algorithm's iterative nature allows for continuous re-meshing of the domain, effectively minimizing the intrinsic mesh dependency.

1. Introduction

Modeling quasi-brittle materials, such as concrete and rocks, is a challenging task. Various methods exist for simulating the fracture of quasi-brittle materials using finite elements [1]. These methods can generally be classified into two categories: continuous and discontinuous. In the continuous approach, cracks are represented in a distributed manner across the finite elements, whereas in the discontinuous approach, cracks are modeled as discontinuities in displacement between adjacent finite elements. The continuous approach is typically implemented using Extended Finite Element Modeling (XFEM) [2]–[5], while the discontinuous approach is commonly realized through Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM) [6]–[8], first pioneered in [9], [10], and selected for use in this work.

The implementation of cohesive elements into the finite element method has proven to be an effective technique for simulating the fracture and fragmentation of materials. In the context of Finite Element Modeling (FEM), simulating fracture involves translating the continuum field into a discrete one. To describe the discontinuity in the discrete field, Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM) can be used as an effective inter-element technique, as demonstrated in the early work of Ortiz and Pandolfi [6], based on the approach by Camacho and Ortiz [11]. These models necessitate the use of cohesive elements which are *a priori* inserted within the mesh, and account for the discontinuity in the displacement field.

Based on their insertion within finite element mesh the cohesive elements can be divided in two groups: intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic cohesive elements are introduced at the pre-processing stage, before the simulation begins. In this approach, all cohesive elements are embedded in the discretized structure, and the mesh connectivity remains unchanged during the entire simulation process. This approach allows for an easy implementation from a mesh representation point of view. However, it also introduces artificial compliance, which depends on the area of the cohesive element surfaces and the cohesive law parameters relative to the bulk element properties. If the crack grows along a pre-defined path with a relatively low number of cohesive elements, the adverse effect is minor. However, for simulations involving a large area or volume of cohesive elements, the adverse effect can be more pronounced and may lead to convergence problems in implicit simulations [8], [12]. Many authors use such approach in their research [13]–[20].

On the other hand, extrinsic cohesive elements are inserted adaptively during the course of the finite element analysis. This approach requires an elaborate updating scheme for the modified mesh, as new nodes and interface elements must be inserted. The extrinsic model eliminates the artificial softening effect present in intrinsic models. However, it also brings complex implementation and parallelism issues. The adaptive insertion of interface elements requires updating the geometrical and topological information as the simulation progresses. For implementing such approach dynamic simulation is required, examples of usage of extrinsic cohesive elements can be seen in [21]–[23].

Both intrinsic and extrinsic approaches have their own advantages and disadvantages. Intrinsic cohesive elements are straightforward to implement and are available in major commercial finite element packages. However, the pre-processing stage to insert interface elements into an existing finite element mesh is quite complex. Extrinsic cohesive elements eliminate the shortcomings of intrinsic cohesive elements, but bring their own complexities to the implementation process. Final choice should be based on the trade-off between computational simplicity and accuracy [12], [22].

As already pointed, intrinsic cohesive elements can cause artificial compliance that is dependent on the size of the cohesive element surfaces and on the ratio of the cohesive strength to the elastic modulus in relation to the bulk element properties. The impact of this is minor if the

crack only grows along a predetermined path with a small number of cohesive elements, but it can be more pronounced in simulations where the cohesive elements are inserted into a large area or volume and lead to convergence problems in implicit simulations [24]. In combination with artificial compliance, it is also pointed in [22] that zero-thickness intrinsic cohesive elements have a small opening before real crack opening which also results in artificial displacements in final results. To adequately address this issue it is necessary to have cohesive stiffness at least 30 times of the elastic modulus of bulk materials as proposed by Tabiei and Zhang in [16]. Therefore, properly chosen small number of cohesive elements exclusively in region of interest together with appropriate cohesive stiffness reduces effect of artificial compliance to negligible level. In this paper intrinsic approach is chosen implemented punctually in the region of expected crack, carefully chosen prior the simulation.

Complete modeling of fracture development within the material demands solving two separate problems. First, it is necessary to determine the crack initiation position, and the second one is to analyze how the crack propagates. Approaches to fracture analysis are different. Robust approaches that are demanding in computation are mitigating the problem of nucleation by enriching the whole domain to enable nucleation in the whole discretized field [25]. Other are trying to analysis the position of nucleation and use CZM only where crack is expected to get efficiency in calculation. For analysis of any of two separate problems criterion for nucleation and/or propagation has to be defined. Among other authors that tried to solve both problems, in their early work Camacho and Ortiz used six node triangular element from discretization of the domain where criterion for implementation of CZM was computed effective stress σ^{eff} at mid-side node compared to the σ_{fr} as presented in [11]. In more recent paper Guiamatsia, Falzon and Davies in [26] used the same approach, proposed in previously mentioned paper, for deciding where does the crack nucleates. In most recent work [27], Zobec and Klemenc presented a different approach with fatigue crack nucleation where initiation is driven by the accumulated damage. In the Paulinos's paper [12] where extrinsic elements are used, criterion for inserting cohesive element is local stress in bulk material compared to a threshold value of the cohesive strength. Similarly to that in [16] Pandolfi and Ortiz implemented an approach in which cohesive elements are inserted when the effective traction acting at a certain element joint reaches the cohesive strength of the material.

Several authors presented the isolated solution for crack propagation for a priori known paths where nucleation location is predefined in specific region, such as boundaries of materials, grains or mastic and reinforcement. Opening of cohesive elements and propagation of the crack in that cases are driven only with constitutive law of the cohesive element. Such example can be seen in the Nguyen research in [8]. Chen et al in [13] by analyzing reinforced asphalt concrete implemented cohesive elements on all the boundaries between mastic and aggregates as well as between all elements used for discretization of mastic. Propagation in that case was driven again only by constitutive model of cohesive elements.

Simulating propagation consist again of two separate elements, first is analyzing “if” the crack propagates while the other one is “where” it propagates. Propagation is regulated with traction separation law which for intrinsic CZM answers on the question “if”, but specific criterion is need for finding the answer on “where”. Some authors like Durand and da Silva in [25], implemented cohesive element between all continuum elements to avoid restricting propagation of the crack. Such approach is computationally more demanding both for implementation of new elements and calculation of displacements and strains.

In course of previously mentioned extrinsic elements, due to their nature driven by implementation and traction separation law they enter directly in the softening, as they do not have initial elastic response, behavior is governed only by parameters of constitutive law for cohesive element. Constitutive law in such case is described with traction separation curve with parameters G_{IC} denoting specific fracture energy, T_n^{max} as cohesive strength in normal direction and δ_n as corresponding separation in case of material failure under mode-I fracture. Still the question of when and where to dynamically insert cohesive elements remains open. Paulino analyzed when does the local strength reaches cohesive strength in bulk material in [12]. Alhadeff et al in [21] studied principal stresses and their directions with respect to nodal location for implementing new cohesive elements.

Principal stresses and their directions are approach that we found to be promising and a path for this research. In their approach with extrinsic elements Alhadeff et al. in their paper [21] used similar approach. Maximum principal stress as criteria was also used in [30] by Bouchard et al. and in [31] by Khoei et al.

In this paper it is presented how to use the principal stress to pair the calculations involving continuum elements with those with adaptively inserted cohesive elements to account for displacement discontinuity due to crack opening. With the developed algorithm it is not necessary to use the computationally demanding approach of inserting the elements along all the boundaries and at the same time the result shows significantly smaller mesh dependency as it involves constant re-meshing. With developed algorithm both of the above outlined problems are simultaneously solved: the problem of crack initiation within the solid domain, and the problem of crack propagation within the domain. The developed method is described in the following section.

2. Developed algorithm for iterative insertion of cohesive elements

The iterative procedure starts by performing the analysis using only continuum elements. These calculation lead to the identification of point within the material where the maximum tensile principal stress reaches previously defined threshold value. The direction of potential crack that would start from that point, and consequently the direction of cohesive elements which are subsequently inserted within computational domain, is determined by the direction of the tensile principal stress. By inserting the first cohesive elements the numerical model for the successive iteration is prepared. Length of a crack step is defined by mesh size around the crack tip. As the computation is iterative with an elevated number of intermediate numerical models, a tradeoff between the accuracy and computing time is made here, by using between 5 to 10 smaller elements around the identified crack zone with respect to the rest of the material.

The model with cohesive elements is now used to predict stress distribution in the presence of opening crack. By applying the same principle for propagation as it was used for finding the point of nucleation it is possible to get more precise information of the stress field and thus better approximate where the crack will continue to propagate. By examining the state of stress in the elements in front of the crack tip and averaging their values for the node forming the crack tip we are calculating precise state stress close to the node of the mesh where the crack tip is at that given moment. This way accurate values of principal stresses and their direction in the position of a crack tip is computed. Bases on this calculation a new direction of next increment of crack propagation is identified.

Algorithm iteratively performs FE simulations and incrementally propagates crack in the domain by analyzing newly obtained stress field for accurate assumption about next iteration. The process is done in this manner because with every increment of crack propagation distribution within “damaged” domain is changing. Thus to have an accurate stress distribution of stresses new analysis is done after every increment of the propagation. Small study was done assuming a crack path only analyzed from stress distribution of continuum domain, it was observed that assumption of the crack path is correct only in the area close to the stress concentration.

Presented methodology is implemented within two dimensional finite element calculations. For this purpose, the cohesive elements are with zero thickness, and hence represented by a single line, with four nodes, where two and two are overlapped. The original mesh is split and the cohesive elements are inserted between two nodes continuum elements. Schematic representation of the process is visualized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Process of inserting cohesive elements

For the robustness of the presented scheme, several things have to be taken into account. The first one is related to the selection of the length along which the crack will be allowed to propagate. Clearly, the longer this length is the less unrealistic result could be. On the other hand by using too short length the iterative simulations would take significantly longer time. A trade-off is made here upon performing comparative numerical analysis and it was selected that the

length should be approximately one quarter of the characteristic element length. It was found that no important modification in crack path was observed if this line was reduced further.

The second feature of importance for the robustness of the presented scheme is related to the identification of crack tip position within the simulations that include cohesive elements. By performing numerical exercises it turned out that the most stable approach is the one where as the crack tip, is considered the part of the continuum that is adjacent to the cohesive elements corresponding to the first cohesive element that is completely degraded. The process is symbolically visualized in Figure 2, indicating the elements used for stress around crack tip calculations.

Figure 2: Continuum elements that are used to evaluate stress at the crack tip – at the figure denoted as 110 and 107.

Sequence of the operations of the developed algorithm is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Operation sequence for the developed algorithm of cohesive element insertion

3. Numerical exercise to test the developed algorithm

For testing the developed algorithm the simulation of the wedge splitting test was adopted. This test is commonly applied to assess the specific fracture energy of materials. In the present context it represents a good platform as it possesses the zone where the crack should initiate, and while in principle symmetric, in practice due to the presence of diverse asperities results in a crack path that is not strictly a straight line.

For modeling purposes in this exercise, for the bulk material a linear elastic response was assumed. Typical values for refractory porous ceramic materials were attributed to the materials, specifically with Young's modulus equal to 22GPa, and Poisson's ratio equal to 0.07. Alternatively, elsto-plastic response could be taken, which was here omitted to mitigate the computing time. However, its application does not represent a limitation of the method, and is straight-forward to implement only with the cost of increased computing time. Cohesive elements are modeled with typical traction-separation law, with the behavior as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Traction-separation law for modeling cohesive elements

With this constitutive model the response of the element is determined by two parameters: threshold in traction up to which the material behaves elastically, and the specific fracture energy which governs the softening part of the response. In this study linear degradation was adopted, alternatively an exponential one could be used. Stress threshold was assumed to be equal to 4.5MPa, and the specific fracture energy to be equal to 300 N/mm, which are typical properties for refractory materials.

The initial mesh adopted to model the test is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Initial finite element mesh to model wedge splitting test

During the numerical exercises, several different finite element meshes were used, and it was found that the overall mesh size does not significantly affect the global final result, both in terms of crack path identification and in terms of overall energy dissipation. In contrast, a more crucial factor is the length over which the iterative cracks are allowed to propagate. Figure 6 illustrates this by comparing two intermediate solutions with different finite element meshes, but both using a relatively long length for the initial crack propagation.

Figure 6: Two different intermediate solutions with relatively long length of crack propagation

By maintaining the crack propagation length as defined in the previous subsection, a significantly smaller discrepancy between results with different meshes is achieved. A typical representative of these results is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: An intermediate (left) result and the final one corresponding to the crack which propagated through the whole sample

The figure presents two stages: one corresponding to the intermediate result, where the crack has propagated to approximately two-thirds of its total length, and the other representing the final scenario. The crack path is generally centered but exhibits a slight deviation, which is commonly observed in experimental results as well.

Here a comment on the efficiency of presented algorithm is in place. Presented simulations were performed on a Intel’s processor “i5-10300H” – 10th generation while using all 8 of its cores that are working on 2.5 GHz and are equipped with 8 GB of RAM. To reach the final solution that is depicted in figure 7 it was required about 55 minutes to obtain full crack path trajectory. The number of iterations was equal to 62 iterations. Considering that the calculation have been performed on a regular laptop computed the obtained result can be treated as rather good.

4. Concluding remarks and future prospects

This paper presents a novel algorithm for the automatic insertion of cohesive elements within the computational domain. The proposed algorithm does not require the a priori insertion of cohesive elements, making it a more efficient alternative to computationally intensive approaches that place cohesive elements throughout the entire domain. While the calculations involve multiple iterations, which extend the computing time, the iterative nature of the algorithm also allows for

re-meshing the computational domain and adjusting the direction of cohesive elements according to the local stress field. This approach ultimately makes the final results less mesh-dependent and enables the simulation of more realistic crack paths. This is supported by the results presented in the paper. All computations were performed on a standard laptop, demonstrating that the method is not time-consuming

Future extensions of this work include coupling the algorithm with elasto-plastic modeling of the surrounding material, which would require modifications to the crack initiation criterion to account for accumulated plastic deformation. Implementing the algorithm presented here for three-dimensional applications is undoubtedly more complex, primarily due to the geometric challenges of domain meshing. However, this does not represent a limitation of the developed methodology.

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